

Regional Parliaments and Covid-19 Crisis Governance in Decentralized Countries

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Abstract

The COVID-19 pandemic was marked by intensified executive dominance and constrained parliamentary activity. While existing research on national parliaments' role in pandemic governance highlights these constraints, it also points to considerable cross-country variation. By contrast, the experiences of regional legislatures remain largely understudied, leaving gaps in our understanding of democratic legitimacy in multilevel governance during emergencies.

This chapter examines the roles and resilience of regional parliaments in decentralized European countries during the COVID-19 pandemic. Focusing on five legislatures with the highest institutional powers—Bavaria, the Flemish Community, Vienna, Zurich, and Madrid—it assesses their involvement in crisis governance. Our analysis shows that their representative and policy-making functions were limited, though to varying degrees. Notably, the parliaments of Bavaria, the Flemish Community, and Madrid distinguished themselves through extensive ex post oversight activities during the first two years of the pandemic.

These findings challenge the view that parliaments were uniformly sidelined in pandemic governance and reinforce recent scholarship emphasizing the variation of parliamentary activity. Moreover, they highlight the important role regional legislatures can play in holding governments accountable during emergencies.

1. Introduction

Parliaments are central to democratic legitimacy, performing essential functions such as representing citizens, enacting legislation, and holding the executive accountable through oversight. In systems of multilevel governance, these core responsibilities are distributed across both national and regional legislatures. While a substantial body of research on crisis governance highlights the expansion of executive power during emergencies, often at the expense of parliamentary involvement, this literature has largely concentrated on national parliaments. In contrast, the roles, responses, and resilience of regional parliaments in times of crisis remain markedly underexamined (but see Höhne 2022 on Germany). This gap limits our understanding of how democratic accountability is sustained or eroded at the subnational level during periods of crises.

Therefore, this chapter examines how and to what extent regional parliaments' roles were limited during the COVID-19 pandemic in Europe. We argue that regional parliaments have faced two key pressures during the crisis. Drawing on literature on decentralized and federal systems in COVID-19 crisis (Chattopadhyay et al, 2021; Steytler, 2022), we discuss how vertical power sharing during the COVID-19 crisis has shaped the role of regional parliaments. We examine how processes of centralization, combined with increased demands for intergovernmental cooperation and coordination, have eroded the institutional space available for regional parliamentary input.

Relying on the literature on parliaments during the Covid-19 pandemic (Cartier, Ridard and Toulemonde, 2020; Chiru, 2024; Kettemann and Lachmayer, 2021; Siefken et al, 2021), we investigate the dynamics of horizontal power sharing between regional governments and parliaments. Existing research on national parliaments indicates that declarations of a national state of emergency or formal delegations of power to the executive often lead to an expansion of executive authority at the national level. In some regions, the declaration of a regional state of emergency curtailed regional parliaments' democratic functions during crises. In many cases, emergency frameworks relegated regional parliaments to roles of ex-post oversight and ratification, thereby diminishing their influence during the crucial early stages of crisis management. Additionally, crisis measures such as social distancing disrupted parliamentary functioning during the initial phase of the pandemic, leading to interruptions and prompting reforms to procedural and operational rules in parliaments both at the national and the regional level.

Given these various pressures, this chapter analyzes how regional parliaments' roles were constrained and how they evolved during the COVID-19 pandemic by differentiating between their representative, legislative, and oversight functions. The empirical analysis focuses on the most powerful regional parliaments in federal and regionalized states representing the wealthiest and most populous regions within their countries because these parliaments play a significant role in contributing to the democratic legitimacy of multilevel political systems and were best positioned to play a significant role in COVID-19 crisis governance.

Our analysis of the regional parliaments of Bavaria, the Flemish Community, Madrid, Vienna, and Zurich shows that their roles were constrained during the COVID-19 pandemic, though to varying degrees. The findings reveal substantial differences in activity levels across the five cases. While all parliaments experienced disruptions or changes in their representative functions and exercised only limited influence on policy-making, the parliaments of Bavaria, the Flemish Community, and Madrid stood out for their extensive ex post oversight, actively scrutinizing and holding their regional governments to account. These results challenge the notion that parliaments were uniformly sidelined

in COVID-19 crisis governance and provide new evidence that parliamentary roles varied not only across countries but also across regions.

In doing so, our study advances debates on democratic legitimacy in multilevel governance during crises, which often focus exclusively on vertical power sharing between national and regional governments while overlooking horizontal power dynamics at the regional level. Furthermore, our comparative perspective contributes to parliamentary research, which has traditionally neglected regional legislatures, by demonstrating their potential significance in times of emergency.

The chapter unfolds as follows. Section Two surveys the current research on how parliaments navigated the COVID-19 crisis, with particular attention to their different functions. Section Three explains our framework for assessing the constraints on regional parliaments, distinguishing between their representative, legislative, and oversight roles, and sets out the reasoning behind our case selection. Section Four brings these concepts to life through five case studies of regional parliaments. Section Five steps back to draw comparative insights, and the final section wraps up with conclusions and potential paths for future research.

2. Parliaments in crisis times

Parliaments are foundational institutions in democratic systems, entrusted with a range of core functions: **representation, legislation, and oversight**, including **budgetary control**. These functions are essential not only for shaping policy but also for ensuring that governments remain accountable to the public. During the COVID-19 pandemic, however, the capacity of parliaments to fulfill these roles was often curtailed—either due to public health measures, legal emergency frameworks, or shifts in executive-legislative power balances. In the following, we discuss how the COVID-19 crisis impacted each function, building on insights from the current literature.

Representation

Parliaments represent the voices and interests of the public, providing a forum for debate and the articulation of diverse societal views. This function is especially important in times of crisis, when the public needs to feel their concerns are being heard and addressed. The pandemic, however, disrupted representational processes in multiple ways. Physical distancing rules and lockdowns made it difficult for members of the parliament (MPs) to meet with constituents, hold public consultations, or even convene in parliament (Waismel-Manor et al, 2022). Most legislatures adopted organizational reforms and technological tools to enable hybrid virtual plenary and committee meetings (Diaz Crego and Kotsanidis 2020, pp. 30–32; Griglio, 2020; Pedersen and Borghetto, 2021; Siefken et al, 2021).

Legislation

The legislative function enables parliaments to create, debate, and amend laws. In ordinary times, this process ensures transparency, pluralism, and procedural checks before laws are enacted. During the pandemic, however, this function was frequently disrupted. Many governments invoked emergency powers based on the constitution that allowed them to adopt laws or regulations by decree (Ginsburg and Versteeg, 2021). To prevent potential abuse, most constitutional emergency regimes incorporate safeguards by mandating checks and balances, with parliaments playing a significant role in their

enforcement. For instance, most constitutions require their parliaments to either declare or at least validate the state of emergency. Some further prohibit the dissolution of parliament during a state of emergency or set automatic expiration dates on emergency powers requiring parliamentary approval for their extension.

In some cases, parliaments formally delegated legislative authority to the executive through ordinary legislation, enabling swift responses to a rapidly evolving public health crisis—a practice Ginsburg and Versteeg (2021) term statutory authorization. In addition, Epidemic Acts and other laws often empower governments to declare certain types of emergencies. While such declarations typically require parliamentary authorization and in some cases can also be made by parliaments themselves (Bolleyer and Salát, 2021), the urgency of the situation was sometimes used to justify bypassing standard legislative processes. This occasionally resulted in the marginalization of parliament, with laws adopted without meaningful debate or consultation, and with limited influence over executive decrees. Even where parliaments continued to operate, procedures were sometimes streamlined, reducing opportunities for amendment or opposition input.

Oversight of the Executive

Parliaments are also tasked with scrutinizing the actions of the executive branch, holding ministers accountable, and ensuring that power is exercised within the law. This oversight function includes questioning ministers, launching inquiries, and reviewing policy decisions (Pelizzo and Stapenhurst, 2012; Schnapp and Harfst, 2005).

In the initial phase of the pandemic, when some parliaments were suspended or went into recess, their oversight weakened. However, once parliaments resumed their activities, they returned to using standard oversight instruments. MPs engaged in emergency policymaking through government statements and questioning during plenary sessions (Griglio, 2020). Oversight through committees was also significant (Navarro and Raunio, 2025).

A key area of parliamentary oversight during the pandemic concerned budgetary control over national and EU-level emergency measures (Griglio, 2020; OECD, 2020). Parliaments are typically responsible for approving national budgets and scrutinizing public spending. This role becomes particularly crucial during crises, when governments introduce large-scale emergency spending and economic stimulus packages. During COVID-19, governments rolled out extensive fiscal measures, but in many countries, parliaments had limited time or capacity to review these packages. Fast-tracked budget processes, bundled spending bills, and minimal debate contributed to superficial or delayed scrutiny of public expenditures. In certain instances, executive branches reallocated funds or created extra-budgetary mechanisms without parliamentary approval, although in some cases, finance committees were involved in budget-related decisions.

Apart from standing committees, many national and regional parliaments established ad hoc committees (Szöcsik, 2025). Most of these special committees focused on reviewing governments' crisis governance, while inquiry committees often investigated potential corruption in public procurement of sanitary materials. Both have been discussed in studies examining the role of parliaments during the pandemic.

3. Assessing regional parliaments' functions during the COVID-19 pandemic

To assess the extent to which regional parliaments' involvement in COVID-19 crisis governance was limited, we first discuss the multilevel dynamics of COVID-19 crisis governance in each case study. During the different phases of Covid-19 pandemic, COVID-19 crisis governance was to a different degree decentralized in regionalized and federal states took. In particular, in the beginning of the pandemic centralizing tendencies were rather strong which limited both the involvement of regional governments and parliaments (reference to other chapters). Table 1 outlines the framework used to assess the representative, legislative, and oversight functions of the five regional parliaments discussed in the following section.

Table 1. Assessing regional parliaments' functions during a crisis

	Weak	Powerful
Representation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Complete suspension of activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation of parliamentary procedures to ensure continued functioning, such as lowering quorum requirements and introducing virtual meetings
Policy influence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No required consent to the declaration of a regional emergency • No impact on restrictive and financial measures 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The right to declare a regional emergency • Required swift approval of an extension of the state of regional emergency • Impact on restrictive and financial measures
Oversight	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weak use of regular oversight instruments • Formation of special and inquiry committees 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extensive use of regular oversight instruments in the plenum and in committees • Establishment of extra-ordinary oversight instruments • Formation of special and inquiry committees

In our analysis, we focus on the most powerful regional parliaments that most significantly contribute to the legitimacy of European multilevel democracies. Since there is no comparative data available on the institutional strength of regional parliaments, we turn to various conceptualizations and measurements of the institutional strength of national parliaments. Although regional parliaments vary significantly across and within countries, we assume that regional parliaments generally reflect the characteristics of the national parliament in each country. Following these arguments, we first select countries within we select regional parliaments in a second step. In this first round, we select national parliaments in regionalized and federal countries with high institutional power along different dimensions. Parliamentary powers have been assessed along multiple dimensions. Following Sieberer (2011), we focus on three key aspects relevant to parliaments' role in COVID-19 crisis governance: direct policy influence, ex-post control, and the strength of the committee system. Switzerland stands out for its strong direct policy influence (Bailer and Bütikofer, 2023), while the parliaments of Austria and Spain are particularly strong in terms of ex-post control. Austria and Belgium distinguish themselves through the strength of their committee systems. Additionally, we include Germany, as it exhibits the

highest level of oppositional parliamentary power among Europe’s decentralized and regionalized countries (Garritzmann, 2017).

In a second step, we selected regional parliaments within these countries that represent the wealthiest and most populous regions, and exhibit the greatest institutional capacity, as indicated by the number of regional parliamentary representatives. Given these selection criteria, we included the parliaments of Free State of Bavaria, the Flemish Community, the autonomous community of Madrid, the federal state of Vienna, and the canton of Zurich.

Table 2 provides an overview of key characteristics of the selected regional parliaments. They vary considerably in the size of the populations they represent: the 180 members of the Zurich Cantonal Council represent only about 1.5 million people, whereas the 205 members of the Bavarian Landtag represent more than 13 million. Although all the selected parliaments represent comparatively wealthy regions, Zurich stands out as one of the wealthiest regions in Europe. Finally, between 2020 and 2022, Vienna was the only selected region with a left-wing government; all others were predominantly right-wing.

Table 2. Overview of the selected regional parliaments

	Landtag of Bavaria	Flemish Parliament	Assembly of Madrid	Landtag of Vienna	Cantonal Council of Zurich
Population ¹	13’124’737 (15.8%)	6’639’005 (57.6%)	6’720’310 (14.2%)	1’911’191 (21.4%)	1’539’275 (17.9%)
Economic wealth ²	133	115	125	144	186
Number of MPs	205	124	136	100	180
Government coalition between 2020 and 2022	Right-wing (CSU and Freie Wähler)	Right-wing (N-VA, CD&V and Open Vld)	Right-wing (PP ³)	Left-wing (SPÖ)	Right-wing ⁴ (5 of 7 members of the Executive Council belong to right-wing parties)

4. Case studies

The Landtag of Bayern

¹ Population on 1 January 2020 by Eurostat (demo_r_d2jan)

² Regional gross domestic product (PPS per inhabitant in % of the EU27) in 2019 by NUTS2 (nama_10r_2gdp)

³ PP formed a coalition with Ciudadanos until March 2021.

⁴ Note that cantonal governments do not operate following the government-opposition divide in Switzerland.

Germany's COVID-19 crisis governance operated under a statutory framework based on the federal Infection Protection Act (*Infektionsschutzgesetz*, IfSG), which governs the prevention and management of communicable diseases (Kaiser and Hensel 2021). The Länder are responsible for implementing the IfSG (Klafki and Kießling, 2020). Through administrative decrees, they determine the introduction, modification, or lifting of specific measures. The federal government may only issue recommendations, thereby facilitating coordination while allowing the Länder significant discretion in shaping their own responses (Hegele and Schnabel, 2021).

To coordinate the measures implemented by the Länder through their own administrative decrees, the long-standing Conference of the Premiers (*Ministerpräsidentenkonferenz*), which brings together the prime ministers of the sixteen Länder, was elevated into an ad hoc Federal-State Conference (*Bund-Länder-Konferenz*, BLK). The BLK made decisions by consensus. However, these decisions had no direct legal effect and were not binding until formally implemented. The Länder parliaments implemented these decisions without having the opportunity to scrutinize or influence them.

Soon after the pandemic had reached Germany, the Infection Protection Act was reformed. The lower chamber of the federal parliament (*Bundestag*) adopted a legal framework for an 'epidemic emergency of national concern' with the consent of its upper chamber (*Bundesrat*). This emergency had to be formally declared by the Bundestag, which it did on 25 March 2020, the same day it passed the bill. The declaration of an 'epidemic emergency of national concern' remained in effect until 25 November 2021. During this time, the Bundestag authorized its extension on four occasions. With the declaration of an 'epidemic emergency of national concern', the Federal Ministry of Health received more competences. The country report SGEAI 1.0 stresses that the expansion of these competences did not result in the reduction of the competences of the Länder. Kuhlmann and Franzke (2022, p. 321), however, argue that the increase of the competences de facto led to tendencies of centralization. Moreover, they point out that the Ministry of Health's authority to enact exceptions to the IfSG through simple statutory ordinances without parliamentary approval or consultation with the Länder or the Bundesrat is regarded by some legal scholars as unconstitutional (Thielbörger and Behlert, 2020), or at least constitutionally questionable.

Following the expiration of the national epidemic emergency declaration in November 2021, the regulations were modified to allow the Länder to maintain certain protective measures until 19 March 2022. The Länder could apply the relevant measures listed if their parliaments declared a concrete danger of the epidemic spread of COVID-19.⁵ The parliaments of almost all Länder, except Rhineland-Palatinate, Saarland, and Bavaria, determined the existence of a concrete danger under the Infection Protection Act at the end of 2021, which remained in effect until spring 2022.

Bavaria declared a 'state of catastrophe' under its existing Disaster Control Act⁶ (Bayerische Staatskanzlei, 2020). It did so during three separate periods: from 16 March to 16 June 2020, 9 December 2020 to 6 June 2021, and 11 November 2021 to 10 May 2022. The first declaration was by the Bavarian disaster control authority, whereas the latter two were by the Bavarian State Ministry of the Interior, for Sport and Integration. This declaration empowered the authority to direct all relevant organisations and agencies in efforts to manage the COVID-19 pandemic. The Bavarian state parliament does not have the competence to make such a declaration, nor is its consent required.

⁵ § 28a(8) IfSG

⁶ § 4(1) BayKSG

Representation

Three days after the initial declaration of a state of catastrophe, the Landtag President Ilse Aigner delivered a speech praising the Minister President and the Bavarian government for their swift decision-making and emphasized that the “Bavarian Landtag, as the highest constitutional body, remains fully operational and capable of making decisions at all times”⁷

To ensure the continued operation of parliament during the pandemic, Aigner announced special measures regarding the parliamentary procedures. These measures concerned the conduct of the sessions, access regulations, and the establishment of a task force composed of faction leaders to enable swift decision-making at the leadership level (Bayerischer Landtag, 2020b, pp. 5216–5219). Furthermore, during this first period following the declaration of a state of catastrophe, the quorum was lowered to one-fifth of the members of parliament.⁸ The parliamentary groups unanimously agreed not to challenge the quorum and to continue adhering to the regular majority requirements. This decision, at least on its face, stood in tension of the Bavarian Constitution⁹. The Bavarian Constitutional Court reviewed the matter but ultimately did not raise any objections. Over the course of the pandemic, the rules on quorum evolved and were adapted to the circumstances: the one-fifth rule was extended several times and later increased to require the presence of half the members until it was able to convene again with full attendance on 22 September 2021 (Bayerischer Landtag, 2021).

On 20 April 2020, the Bavarian Landtag amended its Rules of Procedure¹⁰, authorising the live broadcasting of committee sessions. While plenary debates had been publicly livestreamed since 2005, this had not previously been the case for committees (Bayerischer Landtag, no date). The amendment addressed the institutional disruptions caused by COVID-19 and provided a legal framework to legitimise and safeguard decisions made by parliament under these exceptional conditions. It additionally regulated the voting procedures (including the reduced quorum), legislative deliberations, limited committee composition, and the remote participation of members and experts via video conferencing (Bayerischer Landtag, Protocol, 2020b, p. 5376).

The provision expired at the end of March 2022. In the following plenary debates, a compromise was reached in May: the press was granted permanent digital access to committee sessions, while public livestreams would be provided only in cases of exceptional public interest (Bayerischer Landtag, 2022, Press).

Policy influence

Restrictive measures such as contact limitations, curfews, mask mandates, and bans on public events were primarily enacted by the Bavarian State Government rather than the parliament. The legal basis for these actions was provided by the nationwide Infection Protection Act (IfSG), along with corresponding regulations and general administrative orders at the state level. During the declared state of catastrophe (March to 16 June 2020), the Bavarian State Government exercised expanded powers under the BayKSG and acted without prior parliamentary involvement or approval.

⁷ Quelle

⁸ Art. 23(1 and 2) of the Bavarian Constitution

⁹ Art. 23(2) of the Bavarian Constitution

¹⁰ §193a Geschäftsordnung für den Bayerischen Landtag (BayLTGeschO)

Parliament's role for these measures was largely limited to oversight and political commentary, including plenary debates, urgent motions, committee hearings, and individual parliamentary questions or interpellations (Bayerischer Landtag, 2024).

However, the President of the Parliament emphasised that public acceptance and transparency of the measures required open parliamentary debate (Bayerischer Landtag, Press, 2020d). As the pandemic progressed, calls for increased parliamentary participation intensified (Bayerischer Landtag, Protocol, 2020b, p. 5429; Bayerischer Landtag, Protocol, 2020c, p. 5855; Bayerischer Landtag, Protocol, 2020d, p. 7808; Bayerischer Landtag, Press, 2020c) and there were several sessions in which the parliament questioned the government to increase participation; however, the decision-making authority in most acute situations remained concentrated within the executive (Bayerischer Landtag, Press, 2020e).

In contrast to the restrictive measures, the Bavarian Parliament's involvement in financial responses to the COVID-19 pandemic was both central and legally required. The legal basis for this obligation derives from the Bavarian Constitution¹¹, the Budgetary Regulations of the Free State of Bavaria (BayHO), and the 2019/2020 Budget Act, including its amendments¹².

As early as March 2020, the Landtag swiftly adopted a supplementary budget for 2019/2020, establishing an initial €10 billion 'Bavarian Corona Protection Shield,' later increased to €20 billion. This special fund was financed by invoking the constitutional exemption from the debt brake, which was only reinstated in 2023 (Scope Ratings GmbH, 2025). The temporary suspension of the debt brake was subject to parliamentary debate after the Minister President's statement on 19 March 2020 (Bayerischer Landtag, Protocol, 2020a).

The allocated funds supported medical care, procurement of protective equipment, and emergency aid for businesses to mitigate the impact of the pandemic (Bayerischer Landtag, Press, 2020a, b). The creation of the BayernFonds (a special fund for corporate equity stakes and guarantees) was likewise authorised and approved by parliamentary decision (Bayerische Staatsregierung, 2020). While the State Government prepared the aid packages and special funds, they only became legally effective through parliamentary approval following detailed deliberations in both the Budget Committee and the plenary.¹³ Most parliamentary factions supported the measures, with some proposing clarifications or amendments during committee work that were mostly adopted. The opposition, though generally in favour, often tied its approval to demands for transparency and strict parliamentary oversight, including regular reporting by the State Government on the allocation and use of funds (e.g. Bayerischer Landtag, Protocol, 2020a, p. 5260).

Oversight

Despite the comparatively strong role of the executive during the pandemic, the Bavarian Landtag made intensive use of its regular parliamentary oversight instruments. The following tools are at its disposal: **Written questions**¹⁴ (*schriftliche Anfragen*) may be submitted by individual MPs, must be concise and factual, and must concern matters within the competence of the State Government. If no response is received within four weeks, the question may be escalated as a **question to the plenary**¹⁵ (*Anfragen*

¹¹ Art. 81(1) Bavarian Constitution

¹² e.g. Art. 2a(1) BayHO

¹³ Protocoll of the sessions in Spring 2020

¹⁴ §§ 71–72 BayLTGeschO

¹⁵ § 74 BayLTGeschO

zum Plenum). These are limited to three sub-questions, must be answered within three days, and are published alongside the response. A parliamentary group or at least 20 MPs are allowed to submit **major interpellations**¹⁶ (*grosse Anfragen*) addressing particularly significant issues. They are answered in writing, with the option of a plenary or committee debate no sooner than one and no later than six working weeks following submission. **Immediate information requests**¹⁷ (*unmittelbare Auskunftsverlangen*) permit MPs to address urgent factual questions to the government at any time, including outside parliamentary sessions. Finally, the instrument of the **urgent debates**¹⁸ (*aktuelle Stunden*), enables spontaneous debate on matters of pressing public interest at the beginning of a regular plenary session. It is held upon request by a parliamentary group and is not followed by a resolution. Furthermore, the Landtag of Bavaria has also the right to form inquiry committees¹⁹.

These instruments were extensively used by MPs to monitor the government's management of the COVID-19 crisis: 1,071 written questions, 1,101 plenary questions, 4 major interpellations, 18 information requests, and 41 urgent debates.²⁰ In addition, at the end of 2021, an inquiry committee was established to investigate potential misconduct by the competent state authorities of the Free State of Bavaria, the responsible ministries, members of parliament, civil servants, and political decision-makers in the awarding, brokering, and acceptance of contracts and agreements, as well as in the initiation of economic decisions. The committee was initiated by the parliamentary groups of Bündnis 90/The Greens, SPD, and FDP, and its establishment was supported by all parliamentary groups. Not surprisingly, the governing and opposition parties remained divided over the findings of the inquiry committee's final report (Wilsdorff, 2023). While the opposition claimed there was evidence that some CSU politicians had engaged in corrupt practices during the early pandemic mask procurement process, the CSU committee chairman maintained that the investigation had uncovered no proof of cronyism or favoritism, insisting that all actions had been conducted in accordance with the law. Nevertheless, both sides acknowledged the inquiry's value in uncovering new facts and agreed on the need for follow-up measures. As a result, the Members of Parliament Act²¹ was significantly tightened: income disclosure was made mandatory, deals between MPs and the state were prohibited, and a lobbying register was introduced to help restore public trust.

The Flemish Parliament

The Belgian Constitution does not provide for the possibility of any kind of a 'state of emergency' (Slautsky et al. 2021). In addition, at the onset of the pandemic, Belgium did not have an Epidemic Act.

On 13 March 2020, in accordance with pre-pandemic regulations, the Federal Minister for Home Affairs adopted a Ministerial Decree which transferred the management and the coordination of the public response to the crisis to the Federal Government based on the Civil Protection Act, the Police Force Act, and the Civil Security Act (Slautsky et al, 2021). Although it was not put to a vote, and was not controlled by Parliament, the decision was enacted with broad parliamentary support.²² In the following, the

¹⁶ §§ 67–70 BayLTGeschO

¹⁷ § 75 BayLTGeschO

¹⁸ §§ 65–66 BayLTGeschO

¹⁹ § 30 BayLTGeschO

²⁰ We searched the Bavarian Landtag's database

(<https://www.bayern.landtag.de/parlament/dokumente/drucksachen?dokumentenart=Drucksache>) using the keyword "Covid."

²¹ Bavarian Members of Parliament Act (BayAbgG)

²² <https://www.lachambre.be/doc/PCRI/html/55/ip027x.html>

Minister for Home Affairs enacted a series Ministerial Decrees to slow down the spread of COVID-19, by prohibiting activities of a cultural, social, festive, sporting, or recreational nature and by providing for the closure of most shops.

At the end of March, two Special Powers Acts were adopted at the federal level, with broad parliamentary support. Parliament granted special powers to the Federal Government for three months (30 March–30 June 2020). The enabling statutes provided that Parliament had to confirm the special powers decrees adopted by the executive within one year after they entered into force. If not, the regulations would lose their validity. The enabling statutes also provided that the Government could only use its special powers to fight the COVID-19 pandemic and alleviate its consequences.

Although Ministerial decrees were enacted solely by the Minister for Home Affairs until October 2021, the successive Ministerial Decrees establishing or relaxing the lockdown were all extensively discussed within either the National Security Council (*Nationale Veiligheidsraad*, NVR) (until September 2020) or the Concertation Committee (*Comité de concertation/ Overlegcomité*, CCO) (from October 2020) before their adoption. During the health crisis, the NVR also included the Minister Presidents of the federated entities as many measures adopted at the federal level to fight the pandemic have had an impact on matters pertaining to the Regions and Communities. The NVR remains, however, a federal entity in which the Regions and Communities can only take part upon invitation from the Federal Government. The replacement of the NVR by the CCO in October 2020 signaled a desire by the Regions and Communities to have greater influence in developing the Belgian strategy against the pandemic. The CCO is composed of ministers from the various Belgian executives, with the Federal Government and the regional and community executives represented on equal footing. Regional parliaments therefore did not have an impact on these Ministerial decrees.

Responding to the uncertainty created by the litigation regarding the legal bases used for the first health measures, the Federal Government announced in the early days of 2021 the drafting of a Pandemic Act which was adopted in August 2021 and entered into force in October 2021. Since then, and until 11 March 2022, the Pandemic Act replaced the previous legal bases for health measures.

The Pandemic Act provides for a two-step procedure in the event of an ‘epidemic emergency’. When the conditions are met for an epidemic emergency, the King declares a situation of epidemic emergency for a period of time which cannot exceed three months. The decision is based on a risk analysis from experts advising the Government. A new Royal Decree may prolong the situation of epidemic emergency for a further period of up to three months. The Royal Decree declaring or extending a situation of epidemic emergency must receive legislative confirmation within 15 days. When a situation of epidemic emergency is declared, the King (or the Minister for Home Affairs when the measures cannot be delayed) may enact health measures to control the epidemic. Where local circumstances so require, the Pandemic Act also allows provincial governors and municipal mayors to enact stricter measures, in concertation with the other levels of government.

The Pandemic Act organizes specific forms of parliamentary oversight during situations of ‘epidemic emergency’. Firstly, the Royal Decree declaring the epidemic emergency must be confirmed by Parliament within 15 days. The legislative confirmation of the first Royal Decree declaring a situation of epidemic emergency was voted on 10 November 2021. Under the Act, the Federal Government must also notify the President of the House of the health measures before they are published, as well as communicate to Parliament the scientific advice on which the measures rely. A monthly report from the Government to the House of Representatives on the situation and the adopted health measures is also

provided for in the Act. Finally, the Act itself was the object of an evaluation in early 2023, which has not led to any change in the Act so far.

Representation

The Flemish Parliament continued to hold plenary sessions during the pandemic, although the first was conducted with limited attendance (Jousten and Behrendt, 2022, p. 242). From 25 March 2020, 16 members were authorized to take part: 15 seats were allocated proportionally among the recognized political groups, and the remaining seat was assigned to the P.V.D.A. The restriction on physical attendance was lifted over the summer of 2020 but reintroduced in October of the same year (Jousten and Behrendt, 2022, p. 253). Committee meetings, however, did not take place between 12 March and 7 April 2020 (Jousten and Behrendt, 2022, pp. 235–236). The parliament also adapted its working methods by introducing new technological tools, though these changes were not formalized in its rules of procedure. Instead, the organization of parliamentary work was overseen by the Enlarged Bureau (Jousten and Behrendt, 2022, pp. 235–236).

Policy influence

The parliament of the Flemish community took action mostly on the basis of specific legal authorizations and was the only federated entity that did not grant special powers to its executive in the COVID-19 context (Popelier and Bursens, 2021, p. 98). Pre-pandemic statutes already gave wide powers to the Flemish Government to handle a sanitary crisis. Nonetheless, on 20 March 2020, the Flemish Parliament authorized the Flemish Government to declare a state of civil emergency for a maximum period of 120 days.²³ The state of emergency was declared on the same day (Bouhon et al, 2020, p. 32). This allowed construction and activities to increase health care capacity in Flanders, and/or the production of medical material to be undertaken without the environmental permits normally required. The Flemish Government was also authorized to suspend, interrupt, or prolong deadlines and adapt procedural and administrative obligations set in primary and secondary Flemish legislation. The Flemish Government declared a second state of civil emergency on 30 October 2020 lasting again 120 days, until 27 February 2021.

By contrast to the Flemish and German-speaking communities, the Walloon Region, the French Community, and the Brussels Region quickly adopted a Special Powers Act on the basis of which the governments made arrangements without prior parliamentary involvement and with the possibility to amend or bypass parliamentary acts. The scope of these special powers was unheard of; moreover, the parliaments of regions and communities that granted special powers had either adjourned or substantially reduced their activities (Bouhon et al., 2020).

Oversight

The plenum has different instruments to oversee the government. Representatives can ask a minister a **short question**²⁴ (*actuele vraag*) on a current topic during the weekly question time in the plenary session that ministers shortly answer on the spot. MPs can initiate **current affairs debates**

²³ Flemish Decree of 20 March 2020 containing measures in the event of a civil emergency in public health, Belgian Official Gazette, 24 March 2020

²⁴ Art. 92 RVP

(*atualiteitsdebat*) containing questions on an actual issue. Representatives can also submit a **written question** (*schriftelijke vraag*) to ministers, who must also provide a written response.²⁵ **Current interpellation**²⁶ (*actuele interpellatie*) on urgent matters of general interest that carry significant political weight. After each interpellation, a representative can submit a motion which the plenary must vote on. This is not possible with ordinary questions. In non-urgent cases, **interpellations**²⁷ (*Interpellatie*) are usually dealt with in committee. In committees, representatives can ask a minister for **clarification**²⁸ (*vraag om uitleg*) in a committee meeting and receives information about its policies. Furthermore, MPs have also the right to submit a motion to establish an **inquiry committee**.²⁹

MPs of the Flemish Parliament made intensive use of these instruments: 132 short questions, 903 written questions, 3 interpellations, 594 requests for clarification, and 10 current affairs debates.

A Member of the Workers' Party of Belgium submitted a motioned to launch an inquiry into the impact of the COVID-19 crisis on Flemish residential care centers which was rejected in the plenum.³⁰ In the following, the Extended Bureau of the Parliament including the leaders of the political groups of the Flemish Parliament approved the establishment of an ad hoc committee to evaluate COVID-19 policy and contribute to the development of a post-pandemic plan. The 'Ad Hoc Committee for the Evaluation and Further Implementation of Flemish Corona Policy' was tasked with reviewing the crisis response and drawing lessons for the future and operated from June to December 2020.

The Assembly of Madrid

Based on the Constitution³¹, the Spanish Government declared a nationwide state of alarm in the form of a royal decree for a total period of three months, from 14 March until 21 June 2020 (Utrilla et al. 2021). It declared it for an initial period of 15 days, and subsequently extended it every fortnight, six times, with the approval of the Congress. Congress had to be informed of the declaration and needed to meet immediately for this purpose. Congress's powers are exclusive when it comes to the authorization of an extension of a state of alarm beyond the period of the initial declaration, during which it can also set the effects and scope of the declaration, such that its powers are not restricted to simply casting a yes or no vote.

The power to declare a state of alarm, which is the least restrictive of the three states of emergency that the Constitution defines, vests solely in the Spanish Government. It enables the Spanish Government to temporarily and partially centralize competences which are otherwise assigned to the Autonomous Communities (ACs), as well as to adopt extraordinary restrictive measures to fight the crisis at hand.

Under this state of alarm, the Spanish Government temporarily took over the exercise of certain health-related competences from the ACs in order to quarantine citizens nationwide and to adopt other restrictive measures based on public health concerns. Any matter of regional competence not expressly exercised by the State remained under the regulatory competences of the ACs.

²⁵ Art. 91 RVP

²⁶ Art. 87 RVP

²⁷ Art. 86 RVP

²⁸ Art. 93 RVP

²⁹ Art. 97 RVP

³⁰ 330 (2019-2020) – Nr. 1 ingediend op 25 mei 2020 (2019-2020) Motie van Jos D'Haese tot uitoefening van het recht van onderzoek naar de aanpak van de coronacrisis in de woonzorgcentra

³¹ Art. 116

During the second wave of the pandemic, from September 2020 onwards, the need for a new state of alarm started to be discussed. In view of the worrying situation in the AC of Madrid, on 9 October 2020 the Spanish Government declared a state of alarm in nine municipalities of Madrid, against the will of its Government. The state of alarm lasted for 15 days and no extension was requested from Congress. In contrast to the approach of Madrid, in late October 2020 some ACs, including Castilla-La Mancha, officially requested the Spanish Government to declare a new nationwide state of alarm. This was declared on 25 October 2020. Unlike the first nationwide state of alarm, the second one enabled the ACs to adapt the application of the concrete extraordinary measures to their territories. The declaration was made for an initial period of 15 days, and on 29 October 2020 the Congress authorized its extension for a further period of six months, until 9 May 2021.

Following the expiration of the second nationwide state of alarm on 9 May 2021, no further use of this constitutional instrument has been made by the Spanish Government. On 27 October 2021, the Constitution Court ruled that two aspects of the second nationwide state of alarm had been unconstitutional, namely (i) its ‘decentralised’ design, whereby the Presidents of the ACs could set restrictive measures necessary to stop the spread of the virus as delegates of the President of the Spanish Government; and (ii) the six-month extension of the declaration, because it was considered that Congress abdicated its oversight function regarding the need for a state of alarm for an excessively long period of time.

Representation

In the initial phase of the pandemic, the Bureau of the Assembly decided to suspend all the activities of the parliament from March 11 for 15 days and prolonged the suspension on March 26 for another 15 days to April 12.³² The Bureau of the Assembly is composed of a president, three vice presidents, and three secretaries. As each parliamentary group is represented, opposition parties were likewise involved in the debate on suspending parliamentary activities.

Policy influence

In contrast to Germany and Belgium, in Spain regions, the autonomous communities cannot declare any type of an emergency within their territories, neither their governments nor their parliaments. During the periods of the nationwide state of alarm, the central government was in charge of crisis responses in health policy. Even though that the Inter-Territorial Council for the Health System, the coordination body of Spain’s regional health system met weekly, these meetings had only informative purposes (Angelici et al, 2023, p. 229). In contrast to the first state of alarm in March, the second was implemented in a decentralized manner and managed primarily by the regional governments (Erkoreka et al. 2021).

³² BOLETÍN OFICIAL DE LA ASAMBLEA DE MADRID / Núm. 45 / 8 de abril de 2020. Acuerdo de la Mesa de la Asamblea, de fecha 26 de marzo de 2020, por el que, considerando la Orden de la Consejería de Sanidad 344\2020, de 10 de marzo y el Real Decreto 463, de 14 de marzo, se prorroga la suspensión de toda la actividad parlamentaria acordada por este Órgano Rector, con fecha de 11 de marzo, por el término de otros quince días naturales, hasta el próximo día 12 de abril, suspensión que comprende las reuniones del Pleno y de las Comisiones, así como las de la Junta de Portavoces y de la Mesa de la Asamblea, salvo que fuera necesario proceder a su convocatoria; así como la suspensión del Registro General de la Asamblea, en los términos que se relacionan.

Oversight

Members of the Assembly can ask **questions for oral answers** in plenary session³³ (*preguntas para respuesta oral en pleno*) or in committees (*preguntas para respuesta oral en comisión*) to the members of the Governing Council³⁴. **Written questions** (*preguntas para respuesta escrita*) can also be asked and must be answered by the Governing Council within twenty days.³⁵ MPs and the Parliamentary Groups themselves may formulate interpellations to the Governing Council.³⁶ Interpellations are presented in the plenum. Any interpellation may give rise to a motion, through which proposals for resolutions may be formulated to the Assembly. MPS can also **request official information**³⁷ (*peticiones de Información al Consejo de Gobierno*) from the Council of Government. Furthermore, two Parliamentary Groups or by one-fifth of the members of the Assembly have the right to propose the formation of an inquiry committee.³⁸

MPs submitted 209 oral questions in the plenum and 76 in committees, along with 1,188 written questions and 3,319 requests for information.³⁹ Parliamentary oversight in Madrid was not only intensive but also marked by strong political polarization, as reflected in the heated disputes over the establishment of inquiry committees.

After the first wave of the pandemic, the Commission of Inquiry into the situation caused by COVID-19 in residential centers for the elderly in the Community of Madrid and the Regional Government's management of the situation from February to June 2020 held 20 meetings was launched. Between July 2020 to March 2021 but was never concluded due to early regional elections in May 2021. After campaigners' calls to restart the inquiry were ignored, they launched the citizen-led commission, led by a former judge from Spain's supreme court. In July 2021, a new inquiry commission related to the COVID-19 crisis was launched, the Commission of Inquiry into the possible impact of the entry of the coronavirus through Adolfo Suárez Madrid-Barajas Airport on the spread of COVID-19 in the Community of Madrid. This commission met 22 times but did not conclude its work (?).

Recently oppositional parties aimed to launch investigation of contracts awarded by the Community of Madrid in the COVID-19 crisis questioning the role of Regional President Ayuso and her husband and brother. As these initiatives were always rejected by Assembly's Board arguing that at investigating events from previous terms are not allowed, the left-wing party Más Madrid filed an appeal at the Supreme Court.

The Cantonal Council of Zurich

The Swiss Federal Constitution uses neither the term *state of emergency* nor the terms *emergency* or *emergency law*. However, it authorizes both the Federal Assembly and the Federal Council to take measures to safeguard internal and external security in the event of serious threats. In practice, parliamentary emergency legislation and emergency ordinances issued by the Federal Council are particularly significant (Belser and Mazidi 2021, p. 69). These general emergency provisions are

³³ Art. 194 of the Rules of Procedure of the Assembly of Madrid (RAM)

³⁴ Art. 196 RAM

³⁵ Art. 198 RAM

³⁶ Art. 199-204 RAM

³⁷ Art. 208, 209 RAM

³⁸ Art. 75 RAM

³⁹ We searched the Assembly of Madrid's database (<https://www.asambleamadrid.es/actividad/iniciativas>) using the keyword "Covid." As a next step, we selected only questions and information requests that were processed.

supplemented by a more specific epidemiological regime, which is outlined in the Constitution and implemented through the Federal Epidemics Act (EpA).

On 28 February 2020, the Federal Council declared a ‘special situation’ under the EpA⁴⁰ and enacted initial measures. In this special situation, the Federal Council had the power to enact measures that typically lie in the cantons’ competences, after having consulted them⁴¹. The Federal Council announced stricter restrictions on 13 March 2020, banning events of more than 100 people, triggering the historical self-suspension of the Federal Assembly on 15 March. On 16 March, it declared an ‘extraordinary situation’⁴² and adopted measures that led to an unprecedented centralization of power in the hands of the federal government within the Swiss federal system. The federal measures temporarily reduced the cantons to mere implementing bodies with very limited autonomy, as their consultation was not mandatory. The declaration of an extraordinary situation also empowered the Federal Council to determine whether such a situation exists, and, if so, to adopt the measures it considers ‘necessary’ for the entire country or for parts of it.⁴³ The consultation of the cantons is also no longer required in this situation. The extraordinary situation lasted until 19 June 2020 and was rescaled then to a ‘special situation’ that lasted until 1 April 2022, when it was lifted by the Federal Council, making it the end of most national COVID-19 restrictions.

Representation

When the Federal Council banned large gatherings mid-March, it also clarified that exemptions could be made if a gathering takes place in the interest of the public. The Health Directorate of the canton Zurich first gave the Cantonal Council a special authorization to hold a session, but then revoked it citing the inability to ensure compliance with hygiene and distancing rules in the town hall. As a result the Zurich Cantonal Council suspended its session like the Federal Assembly, other cantonal parliaments and municipal assemblies (Uhlmann and Scheifele 2020, pp. 7 ff.; Kläy 2020, pp. 35). It resumed its plenary sessions in person on 30 March 2020, under restrictive attendance rules and protective protocols (Kläy 2020, pp. 37). Starting April 2020, it permitted committee and supervisory committee meetings to be held via videoconference for agenda items that required only simple decisions or exchanges of information. However, sensitive matters subject to stricter confidentiality were advised against being handled online (Kläy 2020, p. 40).

Policy influence

Parallel to the declaration of an ‘extraordinary situation’ at the Federal level, the cantonal government declared its own ‘extraordinary situation’ according to Zurich Civil Protection Act (BSG)⁴⁴ on 16 March 2020. This decision was based on the assessment provided by the Cantonal Leadership Organisation (KFO) and aimed at ensuring the implementation of the federal COVID-19 Ordinance 2 and any subsequent federal regulations (Zurich Government Council, 2020a, p. 1).

⁴⁰ Art. 6(2) EpA

⁴¹ Art. 6(2) EpA

⁴² Art. 7 EpA

⁴³ Art. 7 EpA

⁴⁴ Art. 10(1) BSG

According to the Zürich Cantonal Constitution (ZH KV)⁴⁵, the Cantonal Government is empowered to issue emergency decrees even in the absence of a legal basis when public safety is seriously disrupted or likely threatened. These emergency decrees must be submitted to the Cantonal Council for approval without delay, although this approval only has a declaratory effect. Some early emergency measures, however, did not formally constitute emergency ordinances. The Cantonal Government classified these actions, such as individual administrative measures and spending decisions, as falling outside of the scope of ‘emergency ordinances’⁴⁶ and therefore not requiring formal parliamentary approval. Nevertheless, since these measures exceeded its constitutional and legal competences, the government opted to inform parliament and seek its endorsement to ensure democratic legitimacy and transparency (Subkommission, 2021, p. 24). Alongside these emergency measures, the government also issued formal emergency ordinances, which entered into force immediately (Zurich Administrative Court, 4th Division, 2020, E. 1.3).

When the cantonal parliament resumed its sessions on 30 March 2020, it adopted the first two emergency measures proposed by the Cantonal Government (Zurich Government Council, 2020b, p. 2), noting explicitly that it could only approve, reject, refer, or not admit an ordinance, but not amend it (Zurich Cantonal Council, 2020, p. 6). Over the following months, further emergency ordinances were debated, some of which concerned social and economic matters. One such ordinance, on compensation for income loss for daycare centers (approved by the Cantonal Council on 6 May 2020), was later ruled unlawful by the Zurich Administrative Court (2020). The Court held that the emergency ordinance competence⁴⁷ is limited to protecting traditional police interests such as life, property, and freedom, and does not extend to economic and social policy without a specific legal basis (E. 4.2).

On 10 June 2020, the Cantonal Government declared the end of the cantonal ‘extraordinary situation’, in line with the Federal Council’s rescaling to a ‘special situation’ (Subkommission, p. 36). Responsibility for implementing measures under the EpA was returned to the Cantonal Medical Service, while the specialized departments resumed control in their respective areas, handling other pandemic-related measures. However, a ‘superspreader’ case in July prompted the re-establishment of a COVID-19 task force led by the Cantonal Police commander, and further actions to combat the virus were outlined (Subkommission, 2021, p. 36).

In August 2020, the government of Zurich published its own COVID-19 ordinance⁴⁸, empowering the ‘competent cantonal authorities’ to impose measures applying to the entire population without any real consideration of the parliament⁴⁹. Initially set to expire at the end of September 2020, this ordinance was extended several times before ultimately lapsing at the end of March 2021.

Overall, the emergency declarations significantly limited the Cantonal Parliament’s substantive role. Most restrictive measures, including bans on events, closures, curfews, and compulsory mask-wearing, were enacted by the Federal Council, and the canton had almost no influence beyond implementing federal ordinances (Belser and Mazidi 2021, pp. 67-70; Kläy 2020, pp. 36). Parliament’s role was largely confined to being informed or retroactively endorsing measures already in force, rather than shaping their content, reducing its function to that of formal legitimisation (Kläy 2020, pp. 36 ff.).

⁴⁵ Art. 72 ZH KV

⁴⁶ Art. 72 ZH KV

⁴⁷ Art. 72 ZH KV

⁴⁸ V Covid-19

⁴⁹ § 54 Para. 1 Cantonal Health Law (GesG) and § 15 **Enforcement Ordinance on Federal Epidemics Legislation** (cantonal).

Oversight

Members of the Cantonal Council of Zurich have a limited range of oversight instruments at their disposal. Notably, they cannot submit oral questions to be answered on the spot by members of the Cantonal Government. Instead, they may submit **written questions**⁵⁰ (*Anfrage*) on matters concerning the canton, which must be answered in writing by the Cantonal Government within three months. Compared to the other parliaments discussed, this is an extraordinarily long response time; even the five-week deadline for urgent written questions is relatively slow. Members of the Cantonal Council can also submit **interpellations**⁵¹ (*Interpellation*) to request information from the government, provided they are supported by at least 20 members of the Cantonal Council. The Cantonal Government must respond to an interpellation within two months of submission, after which a debate on the matter is held in the Cantonal Council. This marks the end of the procedure, and the matter is considered closed. In addition, Members of the Cantonal Council have the right to initiate **special**⁵² and **inquiry**⁵³ **commissions**.

However, in the Cantonal Council, not only is the range of oversight instruments limited, but their use is comparatively low as well. During the pandemic, up to the end of 2022, only 72 written questions and six interpellations were submitted. To oversee the implementation of the various emergency measures adopted by the Cantonal Parliament, its Executive Committee decided to establish a subcommittee by the Finance Committee and the Government Audit Committee (Kläy 2020, p. 38). This subcommittee compiled a report discussing the implementation of the emergency ordinances by the Cantonal Council. This reports critically noted that it is uncertain whether some emergency ordinances have been deemed unlawful if had they been challenged (Subkommission, 2021, p. 27).

The Landtag of Vienna

In Austria, federal constitutional law does not permit the declaration of a state of emergency (Stöger et al. 2021). It only allows the Federal President—upon proposal by the Federal Government—and state governments to issue provisional ordinances in place of legislation if the federal or state parliaments are unable to function. Since the parliaments remained operational throughout the pandemic, these powers were never exercised (Stöger et al. 2021). Therefore, most of the public health measures were based on the Infectious Diseases Act, the COVID-19-Measures Act and further statutes.

As some of the Infectious Diseases Act's provisions lack precision, they were not sufficiently detailed to support the extensive restrictions on fundamental rights intended to be derived from them (Stöger 2021, Rz. 14). Moreover, the Infectious Diseases Act primarily emphasizes regional actions by district authorities, which function as health authorities, and does not provide clear legal foundations for implementing state or nationwide restrictions on mobility (Stöger 2021, Rz. 15). In early March 2020, as a nationwide lockdown loomed, the Government quickly enacted the COVID-19-Measures Act via MPs pushing it through parliamentary committees rapidly. The National and Federal Councils approved it on 15 March, with backing from opposition parties, taking effect the following day (Stöger 2021, Rz. 15).

⁵⁰ § 59 KRG

⁵¹ § 57 KRG

⁵² § 29 KRG

⁵³ § 115-123 KRG

The COVID-19-Measures Act authorised the Health Ministry to issue administrative decrees prohibiting access to business premises and other specified locations when such measures were necessary to contain the spread of the disease and apply to the entire federal territory. Similar powers were granted to the State Governors for measures covering specific federal states, and to the district administrative authority for actions limited to a district or parts thereof.⁵⁴

The subject matter of ‘public health’ is a federal power in legislation and enforcement, encompassing the control of infectious diseases. Although the federal states were responsible, among other tasks, for legislation and enforcement in areas such as care homes for the elderly and disabled, nursery schools, burial law, and municipal sanitation, the majority of relevant legislation addressing the COVID-19 pandemic has been federal (Stöger 2021, Rz. 7). Despite this, the Länder remained vital, implementing the Federal government's executive powers in various sectors.

Austria's federal system grants Vienna a special status, as it is both a municipality and a federal state. Consequently, its political bodies City Council (*Wiener Gemeinderat*) and State Parliament (*Wiener Landtag*) are unique in that they consist of the same group of representatives, who perform different functions depending on the institutional context (Stöger et al. 2021, Rz 39; Steininger 2008, pp. 4).⁵⁵ This dual structure also shapes the distribution of competences between the two bodies.

The State Parliament enacts and modifies state laws, elects the state government, sends members to the Federal Council, and oversees the state government. The City Council, by contrast, is responsible for the financial management of the entire territory of Vienna, as there are no separate budgets for the federal state and the municipality. It adopts the annual budget⁵⁶, manages municipal finances, oversees the use of public funds, elects the mayor and members of the City Senate, establishes and supervises municipal institutions, decides on all matters within the municipality's own sphere of competence, and enacts municipal decrees.⁵⁷ The two institutions are required to formally separate their sessions.⁵⁸

Representation

The Vienna's State Parliament did not pause its activities during the initial phase of the pandemic. However, on March 26, 2020, the Chairman of the State Parliament announced that all factions had unanimously agreed on a special pandemic arrangement to ensure the continued functioning of political decision-making during the pandemic and emphasized that as Vienna's highest political bodies, the City Council and the State Parliament have a special responsibility (City Council, 26.03.2020, p. 3). The measures included a lowering of the attendance from 100 to 66, which still satisfies the quorum⁵⁹, a new seating arrangement to comply with social distancing rules and a reduction of speaking time to accelerate the sessions, while retaining the opposition's rights to lodge interpellations. The usual participation tools were restricted, with questions to members of the city government limited to written submissions instead of oral questions. The sessions continued to be held in person without a switch to virtual meetings ([Der Wiener Landtag - Abgeordnete, rechtliche Grundlagen und Funktionen](#)).

⁵⁴ §1 and §2 of the COVID-19-Measures Act

⁵⁵ Art. 108 Federal Constitutional Law of Austria (B-VG); §113 Vienna City Constitution (WStV)

⁵⁶ §86 WStV

⁵⁷ §§1, 9 ff. WStV

⁵⁸ §120(1) WStV

⁵⁹ §24(1) Rules of Procedure of the Vienna Parliament mandates at least a third

Policy-making

There were significant differences in policymaking depending on whether the measures were financial or restrictive. Restrictive measures were determined entirely at the federal level, with the federal states left to implement and enforce them. In Vienna, the implementation of nationwide COVID-19 measures took place predominantly within the framework of the so-called indirect federal administration. This meant that the federal government adopted the relevant laws and ordinances (such as the Epidemics Act, the COVID-19 Measures Act, or ordinances mandating mask requirements) while their concrete execution, including monitoring, and enforcement was the responsibility of the Viennese authorities, in particular the Vienna Municipal Administration. There was virtually no discretion regarding the substance of these measures, but some latitude existed in their practical organisation and administrative execution. The minutes of the Vienna City Council reflect this role: they regularly record reports on the status and modalities of implementation, but not deliberations or decisions on the measures themselves.

With regard to financial measures, the separation of competences between the City Council and the State Parliament of Vienna explains differences in the handling of retroactive approvals, which are relevant to the legitimacy of the governmental actions during the pandemic. In the State Parliament, such approvals are not envisaged: There is no provision or established practice allowing the state government to take executive measures without a legal basis and have them later “legalised” by the Landtag. By contrast, the Vienna City Constitution⁶⁰ explicitly allows the City Council to approve certain expenditures or administrative acts retroactively. This competence was invoked multiple times during the pandemic, first, for example, in the 66th session of the City Council on 26 March 2020, when three measures were unanimously approved ex post: the allocation of funds for containing and combating the coronavirus; immediate economic and labour market measures; and crisis management and emergency aid. In addition, the Vienna’s State Parliament enacted several crisis-related laws and amendments in 2020. These included, for example, changes to the Minimum Income Act, the Disaster Relief and Crisis Management Act, the Hospitals Act, and the Act on the Organisation of Tax Administration as part of the COVID-19 Tax Amendment Act.

Oversight

The oversight instruments available to members of the State Parliament include the following: During “question time,” each MP is entitled to address short **oral questions**⁶¹ (*mündliche Anfrage*) to the Landeshauptmann or the responsible members of government. These questions must be answered orally by the recipient in the same public session in which they are raised. The **urgent debate**⁶² (*aktuelle Stunde*) serves as a discussion on matters of pressing current interests within the scope of the state administration or municipal government. No motions or resolutions may be adopted during this debate. **Written questions**⁶³ (*schriftliche Anfrage*) may be submitted at any time to the government, providing a brief justification. The recipient must respond in writing within two months of receipt; however, an oral response is also possible if the proposer consents.

⁶⁰ §§92, 98 WStV

⁶¹ §32 Rules of Procedure of the Vienna State Parliament (GO Landtag)

⁶² §39 GO Landtag

⁶³ §31 GO Landtag

MPs also have the right to submit **motions**⁶⁴ (*Antrag*), that must be supported by at least five MPs. Motions must be dealt with within one month. Finally, members may submit **motions to set up an inquiry commission**⁶⁵ to investigate the administration of politically responsible organs within the autonomous remit of the state, or to review executive actions of organs that are politically accountable in the municipality's own sphere of competence. Such a motion must be supported by at least 30 members and must specify a concrete, current grievance.

These rights were not formally neither changed nor restricted during the pandemic. However, as part of the "Special Faction Agreement on the Pandemic" and pandemic-related organizational measures, oral questions, as previously mentioned, were temporarily handled in writing only, while other interpellation rights remained fully intact ([Der Wiener Landtag - Abgeordnete, rechtliche Grundlagen und Funktionen](#)). Additionally, the speaking times usually allotted to the members were significantly reduced. According to our search of the State Parliament's database, MPs have submitted only 12 oral questions and 4 written questions related to the COVID-19 pandemic.⁶⁶ There was one urgent debate held. Finally, regional government's COVID-19 crisis responses were not reviewed by an inquiry committee.

5. Comparative discussion

Table 3 provides a broad comparative overview of how the functions of regional parliaments were restricted during the pandemic. Regarding the representative function, there is a clear divide between the parliaments of Madrid and Zurich, which implemented a comprehensive pause in their activities, and those that did not. Such pauses are particularly problematic, as opposition parties were not involved in the decision to suspend parliamentary work.

In terms of policy-making influence, apart from the declaration of an emergency at the national level, the declaration of a regional emergency further curtailed the role of regional parliaments. Among the cases discussed, only the Flemish government refrained from declaring a regional emergency. The Bavarian parliament stands out, because of its right to declare one on its own initiative.

When it comes to oversight, the parliaments of the Flemish Community, Vienna and Zurich made limited use of their regular instruments, while the others remained highly active. In Zurich's case, this limitation is compounded by the fact that the Cantonal Council has very few oversight instruments available. The State Parliament of Vienna is notable as the only parliament examined that did not establish a special or inquiry committee to review the government's crisis response.

Overall, the regional parliaments of Bavaria and the Flemish Community played a comparatively stronger role, while the regional parliaments of Vienna and Zurich was the most constrained. The parliaments of Madrid falls somewhere in between. Across all three functions, the parliaments of Bavaria, the Flemish Community, and Madrid demonstrated a high level of ex post oversight, which challenges the notion that regional parliaments were entirely sidelined.

Table 3. Comparative assessment of regional parliaments' functions limitations

⁶⁴ §35 GO Landtag

⁶⁵ §§39a, 39b GO Landtag

⁶⁶ We searched the State Parliament's database (<https://www.wien.gv.at/infodat/>) using the keyword "Covid."

	Weak	Powerful
Representation	Flemish Community, Madrid, Zurich	Bavaria, Vienna
Policy influence	Madrid, Vienna, Zurich	Bavaria, Flemish Community
Oversight	Vienna, Zurich	Bavaria, Flemish Community, Madrid

6. Conclusion

Literature on COVID-19 crisis governance in federal and regionalized states has largely concentrated on vertical relations—that is, the interaction between national and regional governments—and on intergovernmental coordination across countries (Hegele and Schnabel, 2021). This chapter, by contrast, has placed emphasis on horizontal relations at the regional level focusing on the role and resilience of regional parliaments.

Our analysis examined the representative, policy-making, and oversight functions of five regional parliaments using a descriptive comparative approach. In line with recent literature, our findings challenge the common notion that parliaments were broadly sidelined by governments during the pandemic. Instead, we find significant variation across the five cases, with Bavaria, the Flemish Community, and Madrid standing out for their particularly strong ex post oversight. This suggests that regional parliaments can play an important role during crises and, in doing so, contribute significantly to the legitimacy of crisis governance in multilevel systems.

Given the considerable variation highlighted in our study, future research should investigate the underlying sources of these differences. Previous work at the national level has shown that the state of democracy, pre-crisis legal frameworks, patterns of party competition, and coalition politics significantly shaped parliamentary roles (Bolleyer and Salát, 2021; Chiru, 2024). It would be valuable to explore how these factors operate at the regional level, how multilevel dynamics unfold, and whether institutional constraints are more pronounced in subnational settings. Moreover, further research should examine the extent to which regional parliaments have learned from the COVID-19 crisis and whether they have strengthened their roles in anticipation of future emergencies.

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